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FREQUENCY OF DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE AND ITS COMMON FACTORS IN PATIENTS WITH NEW ONSET HEART FAILURE

Dr. Syed Dawood Shah, Dr. Hazrat Ali, Dr. Noor Ahmed Khosa, Dr. Syed Abdul Bari, Dr. Sheikh Ahmed, Dr. Muhammad Samsoor Zarak, Mir Zaman Kasi

Sandeman Provincial Hospital Quetta, Balochistan Pakistan.

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ABSTRACT

Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction is the clinical syndrome of heart failure associated with normal or near normal systolic function. Patients who have heart failure present with dyspnea, orthopnea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea and exercise intolerance, regardless of a preserved or an impaired ejection fraction. Diastolic dysfunction is the most important pathophysiological mechanism ultimately leading to diastolic heart failure. Abnormal cardiomyocyte sodium and calcium handling within myocytes has been proposed as a potential mechanism that contributes to diastolic dysfunction. Risk factors for diastolic dysfunction are older age, female sex, hypertension, ischemia, obesity and coronary artery disease. The rates of death and illness among these patients are high and have not declined, as they have in patients with heart failure and a low left ventricular ejection fraction. The objective of this study is to determine the frequency of diastolic heart failure and its common factors in patients with new onset heart failure. This study was conducted at Bolan Medical College / SPH, Department of Cardiology, Hospital, Quetta. Study design was descriptive cross sectional study and the duration of the study was one year (2012-2013). The total sample size was 205 using 7% margin of error under WHO sample size calculation. More over non probability purposive sampling technique was used for sample collection. All patients both male and female of age more than 20 years admitted to Cardiology Unit with signs and symptoms of heart failure were included while patients having prior history of diagnosed heart failure and on treatment, patients having prior history of coronary artery disease, patients with acute pericarditis, acute myocarditis and unstable angina were excluded. In this study 4% patients were in age range 40-50 years, 28% patients were in age range 51-60 years, 35% patients were in age range 61-70 years and 33% patients were in age range 71-80 years. Mean age was 65 years with SD \pm 1.26. Forty five percent patients were male and 55% patients were female. The frequency of diastolic heart failure was 8% in patients with new onset heart failure in which 60% patients were female gender, 70% patients had hypertension, 11% patients had atrial fibrillation. Our study concludes that the incidence of diastolic heart failure was 8% in patients with new onset heart failure in which 60% patients were female gender, 70% patients had hypertension, 11% patients had atrial fibrillation. Which shows that hypertension and gender in onset of diastolic heart failure was found to be an independent predictor of mortality.

Corresponding author

Dr. Syed Dawood Shah

Assistant Professor

Sandeman Provincial Hospital Quetta

Balochistan Pakistan

Dawoodshah1971@Gmail.Com

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INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease has a major impact on global health. According to the World Health Organization, an estimated 17.1 million people died of cardiovascular diseases worldwide in 2004, representing 29% of all deaths; approximately 23.6 million people are expected to die from these diseases in 2030¹. Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death around the world². Among the cardiovascular diseases heart failure is one of the most common causes of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, and its prevalence is rapidly increasing as the mean age of the population advances³. Heart failure constitutes a pandemic both in developed and developing countries and has not spared any group of people⁴. Despite recent advances in the diagnosis and management of heart failure, the rate of hospitalizations for this condition is increasing. At least 50% of patients present with heart failure despite a normal ejection fraction and are referred to as having heart failure with normal ejection fraction or diastolic heart failure⁵.

Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction is the clinical syndrome of heart failure associated with normal or near normal systolic function⁶. Patients who have heart failure present with dyspnea, orthopnea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea and exercise intolerance, regardless of a preserved or an impaired ejection fraction⁷.

Diastolic dysfunction is the most important pathophysiological mechanism ultimately leading diastolic heart failure. Abnormal cardiomyocyte sodium and calcium handling within myocytes has been proposed as a potential mechanism that contributes to diastolic dysfunction⁸. Risk factors for diastolic dysfunction are older age, female sex, hypertension, ischemia, obesity and coronary artery disease. The rates of death and illness among these patients are high and have not declined, as they have in patients with heart failure and a low left ventricular ejection fraction⁹.

It is necessary to measure left ventricular ejection fraction after confirming the presence of heart failure. If ejection fraction is preserved it is Diastolic heart failure, and if reduced it is Systolic Heart Failure¹⁰. Normal ejection fraction is usually considered as more than 50% but varies in different settings. Non invasive assessment of diastolic dysfunction using Doppler echocardiography provides useful information on the severity of heart failure and its prognosis. The optimal treatment of patients with heart failure and normal ejection fraction has not yet been defined, but the control of systolic hypertension and the avoidance of fluid overload are important¹¹.

Prevalence of heart failure among general population is about 7%-8% with 40-50% patients having diastolic heart failure¹². Patients with diastolic heart failure are usually older (75 years v. 72 years), more often female (66% v. 37%) and more likely to have a history of hypertension (55% v. 49%) and atrial fibrillation (32% v. 24%)¹³.

It has been my observation over time that most of the beds in our unit are occupied by patients with heart failure. Many studies are available regarding heart failure with reduced ejection fraction prevalence but after thorough literature review I could find only a few studies pertaining to diastolic heart failure in Pakistan. Therefore I took up the task to estimate the burden of diastolic heart failure and its various risk factors in our setup by assessing its frequency in patients with newly diagnosed heart failure.

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of this study is to determine the frequency of diastolic heart failure and its common factors in patients with new onset heart failure.

MATHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Bolan Medical College / SPH, Department of Cardiology Quetta. Study design was descriptive cross sectional study and the duration of the study was one years (2012 to 2013). The total sample size was 205 using 7% 12 proportion of heart failure among general population, 95% confidence interval and 3.5% margin of error under WHO sample size calculation. More over non probability purposive sampling technique was used for sample collection. All patients both male and female of age more than 20 years admitted to Cardiology Unit with signs and symptoms of heart failure were included while patients having prior history of diagnosed heart failure and on treatment, patients having prior history of coronary artery disease, patients with acute pericarditis, acute myocarditis and unstable angina were excluded. The above mentioned conditions act as confounding factors and if included had introduce bias in the study results. All the patients presenting to Cardiology unit of SPH hospital Quetta with the first episode of heart failure was included into the study. Written informed consent was obtained. Detailed history and clinical examination was done. Blood pressure was measured on both arms using standard mercury sphygmomanometer. ECG was recorded and detailed echocardiography was done to classify them into diastolic heart failure and systolic heart failure on the basis of ejection fraction. A chest x-Ray PA view was done. All the data was noted down on the proforma annexed. All these observations and measurements were performed by myself and strictly inclusion and exclusion criteria was followed to avoid any bias in data. Prior approval of ethical committee of PGMI was obtained. Data collected was analyzed using SPSS version-15. Frequency and percentage for categorical variables like diastolic heart failure and its common factors including Hypertension, gender and atrial fibrillation was calculated. Mean \pm SD was calculated for numeric variable like age. Heart failure whether diastolic or systolic and its common factors was stratified among gender to see the effect modifications. All results were presented in the form of tables and graphs.

RESULTS

In this study age distribution among 205 patients was analyzed as 8(4%) patients were in age range 40-50 years, 57(28%) patients were in age range 51-60 years, 72(35%) patients were in age range 61-70 years and 68 (33%) patients were in age range 71-80 years. Mean age was 65 years with $SD \pm 1.26$. (table No 1) Gender distribution among 205 patients was analyzed as 92 (45%) patients were male, 113 (55%) patients were female. (table No 2). Frequency of diastolic heart failure among 205 patients was analyzed as 16 (8%) patients had diastolic heart failure while 189 (92%) patients didn't had diastolic heart failure. (table No 3). Common risk factors of diastolic heart failure among 16 patients were analyzed as 10 (60%) patients were female gender, 11(70%) patients had hypertension, 2 (11%) patients had atrial fibrillation. (table No 4). Stratification of diastolic heart failure and common risk factors with age and gender is given in table No 5,6,7,8

TABLE NO 1. AGE DISTRIBUTION.

(n=205).

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
40-50 years	8	4%
51-60 years	57	28%
61-70 years	72	35%
71-80 year	68	33%
TOTAL	205	100%

Mean age was 65 years with $SD \pm 1.26$.

TABLE NO 2. GENDER DISTRIBUTION.

(n=205).

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	92	45%
Female	113	55%
TOTAL	205	100%

TABLE NO 3. DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE.

(n=205).

DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	16	8%
No	189	92%
TOTAL	205	100%

TABLE NO 4. COMMON RISK FACTORS.

(n=16).

COMMON RISK FACTORS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
FEMALE GENDER	10	60%
HYPERTENSION:	11	70%
ATRIAL FIBRILLATION	2	11%

TABLE NO 5. STRIFICATION OF DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE WITH AGE.

(n=205).

DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE	40-50 years	51-60 years	61-70 years	71-80 years	TOTAL
Yes	0	4	7	5	16
No	8	53	65	63	189
TOTAL	8	57	72	68	205

Chi square test was applied in which P value was 0.7738.

TABLE NO 6. STRIFICATION OF DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE WITH GENDER.
(n=205).

DIASTOLIC HEART FAILURE	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
Yes	7	9	16
No	85	104	189
TOTAL	92	113	205

Chi square test was applied in which P value was 0.9247.

TABLE NO 7. STRIFICATION OF COMMON RISK FACTORS WITH AGE.
(n=16).

COMMON RISK FACTORS	STATUS	40-50 years	51-60 years	61-70 years	71-80 years	P VALUE
FEMALE GENDER	Yes	0	2	5	3	0.7208
	No	8	55	67	65	
TOTAL		8	57	72	68	
HYPERTENSION	Yes	0	2	5	4	0.7458
	No	8	55	67	64	
TOTAL		8	57	72	68	
ATRIAL FIBRILLATION	Yes	0	0	1	1	0.8157
	No	8	57	71	67	
TOTAL		8	57	72	68	

TABLE NO 8. STRIFICATION OF COMMON RISK FACTORS WITH GENDER.
(n=16).

COMMON RISK FACTORS	STATUS	MALE	FEMALE	P VALUE
FEMALE GENDER	Yes	4	6	0.7504
	No	88	107	
TOTAL		92	113	
HYPERTENSION:	Yes	5	6	0.9684
	No	87	107	
TOTAL		92	113	
ATRIAL FIBRILLATION	Yes	1	1	0.8836
	No	91	112	
TOTAL		92	113	

DISCUSSION

Cardiovascular disease has a major impact on global health. According to the World Health Organization, an estimated 17.1 million people died of cardiovascular diseases worldwide in 2004, representing 29% of all deaths; approximately 23.6 million people are expected to die from these diseases in 2030¹. Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death around the world².

Our study shows that 4% patients were in age range 40-50 years, 28% patients were in age range 51-60 years, 35% patients were in age range 61-70 years and 33% patients were in age range 71-80 years. Mean age was 65 years with SD \pm 1.26. Forty five percent patients were male and 55% patients were female. The frequency of diastolic heart failure was 8% in patients with new onset heart failure in which 60% patients were female gender, 70% patients had hypertension, 11% patients had atrial fibrillation.

In study conducted by Sánchez MA et al¹⁶ the prevalence of heart failure among general population is about 7%-8% with 40-50% patients having diastolic heart failure.

In study conducted by Tzanetos K et al¹⁷ the patients with diastolic heart failure are usually older (75 years v. 72 years), more often female (66% v. 37%) and more likely to have a history of hypertension (55% v. 49%) and atrial fibrillation (32% v. 24%).

In study conducted by Diller PM et al¹⁸ the frequency of CHF increased with age for men and women (1.3% for patients 45-54 years old to 8.8% for patients > 75 years old). The distribution according to left ventricular ejection fraction and age varied according to sex. Women had later onset of CHF that was predominantly diastolic dysfunction heart failure. Men had proportionately more systolic dysfunction heart failure at all ages. Forty percent of all patients with CHF had diastolic heart failure, and these patients had fewer functional limitations (76% with New York Heart Association classes I and II), fewer hospitalizations for CHF, and a trend toward fewer deaths during the study year compared with patients with systolic dysfunction.

The prognosis of patients with diastolic heart failure, although less ominous than that for patients with systolic heart failure, does exceed that for age-matched control patients.¹⁴ The annual mortality rate for patients with diastolic heart failure approximates 5% to 8%. In comparison, the annual mortality rate for patients with systolic heart failure approximates 10% to 15%, whereas that for age-matched controls approaches 1%. In patients with diastolic heart failure, the prognosis is also affected by the pathological origin of the disease. Thus, when patients with coronary artery disease are excluded, the annual mortality rate for isolated diastolic heart failure approximates 2% to 3%.¹⁵ The other determinants of mortality include age, EF cutoff, and study design. Like prevalence, these are interactive, with the most important determinant being age. In fact, an increasing amount of data suggests that in patients >70 years old, the mortality rates for systolic and diastolic heart failure are nearly equivalent. Morbidity from diastolic heart failure is quite high, which necessitates frequent outpatient visits, hospital admissions, and the expenditure of significant healthcare resources. The 1-year readmission rate approaches 50% in patients with diastolic heart failure. This morbidity rate is nearly identical to that for patients with systolic heart failure.

The mechanisms by which hypertension and visceral obesity lead to impaired LV diastolic function remain to be defined. It has been shown that visceral obesity is associated with diastolic dysfunction, an effect that may be mediated by an obesity-related pro-inflammatory state and/or by suppression of adiponectin expression.¹⁸

Other potential mechanisms whereby Metabolic syndrome contribute to impaired LV diastolic function include endothelial dysfunction, abnormalities in myocardial perfusion and/or metabolic substrate utilization, inflammation and oxidative stress, interstitial fibrosis, impaired ventricular –vascular interaction, and others.

CONCLUSION

Our study conclude that the incidence of diastolic heart failure was 8% in patients with new onset heart failure in which 60% patients were female gender, 70% patients had hypertension, 11% patients had atrial fibrillation. Which shows that hypertension and gender in onset of diastolic heart failure was found to be an independent predictor of mortality.

LIST OF ABRIVATION

CHF	:	CARDIC HEART FALUIR
SPH	:	SANDEMAN PROVICIAL HOSPITAL
LV	:	LEFT VENTRICLE
EF	:	EJECTION FRACTION
WHO	:	WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION

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